

Soil microbiology and biological N fertilizer

Early, uniform stem nodulation in *Sesbania rostrata* after spray of *Rhizobium* culture

A. S. Bhagwat, D. C. Joshua, and C. R. Bhatia, Nuclear Agriculture Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Trombay, Bombay 400085, India

Sesbania rostrata plants grown in pots filled with local Trombay soil did not produce any stem nodules. Plants raised in pots filled with a mixture of local soil and soil from Paddy Breeding Station,

Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore, or inoculated with homogenized stem nodules nodulated profusely.

Those fully grown stem nodules were removed, cleaned in tap water, surface-sterilized with 0.1% HgCl₂ for about 4 min, and washed in sterile distilled water. The nodules were crushed, inoculated in Luria broth (tryptone 1%, yeast extract 0.5%, and NaCl 0.5%), and incubated at 28 °C. After 48 h, the culture was plated on Congo red yeast extract mannitol agar. Colorless mucoid, slow growing colonies were

isolated and tested. One culture (TCSR) was tested in the field.

For field inoculation, culture grown in Luria broth (about 10⁸ cells/ml) was sprayed on 35-d-old *S. rostrata* (25 plants with 4 replications). At this stage plants were 75-80 cm tall and had no stem nodules.

Nodules developed on inoculated plants within 10 d. Stem nodules on 5 plants from each replication were counted 20 d after inoculation.

The rhizobial culture induced early, repeatable nodulation. At 55 d after sowing, the mean number of stem nodules on inoculated plants was 180+16, compared to 22+4 in control plants. This culture is available on request. □

Physiology and plant nutrition

Influence of nitrogen and zinc application on nutrient uptake by rice in different seasons

M. A. Salam, Kerala Agricultural University, Cropping Systems Research Centre, Karamana 695002; and S. Subramanian, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (TNAU), Coimbatore 641003, India

We studied the uptake of major and micro nutrients by rice in three seasons: 1982 southwest monsoon Jun-Oct, 1982 northeast monsoon Oct-Jan, and 1983 summer Feb-Jun. The experiment was

laid out in a factorial combination of 4 levels of N (0, 60, 90, and 120 kg N/ha) and 2 levels of Zn (no ZnSO₄ and 25 kg ZnSO₄/ha) in a randomized block design with 6 replications, in a different field each season.

The soil at TNAU (11 °N, 77 °E and 427 m above mean sea level) was a Vertisol (clay loam) containing 1.1% organic C, 196-9.5-200 ppm available NPK, 598 ppm total soil N, and 0.4 ppm DTPA extractable Zn. The test variety was IR20. Standard management practices were used. Nutrient uptake was estimated using standard procedures.

N benefited uptake of N, P, K, Zn, Fe, Mn, and Cu in all seasons; in general, the effect persisted up to 90 kg N/ha (see table). Zn also increased N, P, Zn, and Fe uptake in all seasons. This can be ascribed to the positive effect of Zn on root dry weight and root volume (data not given).

N-Zn interactions were not consistent, N up to 90 kg/ha and ZnSO₄ at 25 kg/ha increased grain yield in all seasons. Simple regressions and coefficients of determination revealed significant positive correlations in all seasons.

A comparison between seasons showed that uptake of N, P, K, Zn, Fe, Mn, and Cu was low during northeast monsoon season. □

Nutrient and micronutrient uptake by season.^a TNAU, Coimbatore, India, 1982-83.

N and Zn levels	N uptake (kg/ha)			P uptake (kg/ha)			K uptake (kg/ha)			Zn uptake (g/ha)			Fe uptake (kg/ha)		
	SWM	NEM	SUM	SWM	NEM	SUM									
N0	67	46	57	18	13	19	74	74	132	137	97	146	1.18	0.53	1.24
N60	87	55	79	21	16	19	96	95	117	208	159	217	1.68	0.97	1.74
N90	96	60	89	22	18	22	101	136	143	209	168	198	1.62	1.10	1.96
N120	104	70	91	21	17	23	162	142	164	239	181	211	2.00	0.97	1.94
LSD (0.05)	7	7	8	2	1	4	25	20	22	21	16	22	0.17	0.12	0.22
Zn0	84	53	76	18	15	19	101	106	131	185	126	180	1.45	0.84	1.62
Zn1	93	63	81	23	17	22	115	117	146	212	162	206	1.77	0.95	1.82
LSD (0.05)	5	5	ns	1	1	3	ns	ns	ns	15	12	16	0.12	0.08	0.16

^aSWM = southwest monsoon, NEM = northeast monsoon, SUM = summer.